

Jutta M. Street & Emily Pelka

Vol 1:1 2022

According to Webster's dictionary, learning is "the acquisition of knowledge or skill by studying, practicing, being taught, or experiencing something" ("learning"). Most learners tend to acquire higher skill levels with hands-on, or active, learning rather than with passive learning. When the objective is the acquisition of cultural awareness and intercultural competence, the optimal active experience is some type of immersion or in-person contact with an unfamiliar culture. In contrast, traditional classroom instruction on topics related to cultural awareness and intercultural competence tends to produce only small gains in and minimal transfer of these skills in undergraduate students (Sandell & Tupy, 2015). It follows that our efforts to increase cultural sensitivity in undergraduates must be intentional and engaging.

A framework for such an effort is offered by Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory. According to this theory, learning occurs in four stages. The first stage involves a concrete new experience or situation. The second stage involves observation of and reflection on that experience, with particular attention to inconsistencies between understanding and experience. The third stage is abstract conceptualization, or analysis of what has been learned. The fourth stage involves active experimentation with new ideas and new experiences. With their increasing complexity and scope, Kolb's stages provide useful guidance for the development of intentional, active, and high-impact classroom activities that facilitate cultural competence.

For undergraduates, effective teaching must pair active engagement with developmental considerations. In 2004, Milton Bennett introduced his *Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity* (DMIS) which emphasizes that intercultural sensitivity is a developmental phenomenon. Specifically, individuals change over time from an ethnocentric cultural perspective, with denial, defense and minimization to an ethnorelativistic perspective, characterized by acceptance, adaptation, and integration. Employing Bennett's model, Sandell and Tupy (2015) found that a group of American teacher candidate students initially overestimated their intercultural competence; they were more ethnocentric than they thought at the beginning of the study. However, one semester of high-impact activities (e.g., cultural partnerships, frequent reflection papers, etc.) yielded significant gains in understanding and orientations to cultures different than their own. Like teacher candidates, nursing students need to be prepared to interact with people from varied cultural backgrounds (Markey & Okantey, 2019). Undergraduate institutions that aim to prepare students for global citizenship must include cultural competence education across the curriculum.

The intentional facilitation of cultural competence in undergraduates is not a new topic. In 1997, Robinson and Bradley found that engaging undergraduates with other worldviews and guiding them in the examination of multicultural issues, biases, values, and assumptions produced significant gains in knowledge and awareness scores on *The Multicultural Awareness-Knowledge-and-Skills Survey*. However, recent socio-political events, racial/ethnic disparities related to the effects of COVID-19 and pressing social issues have reminded us that culture is a dynamic construct that changes over time. Cultural competence education must keep up with

these changes. Undergraduate faculty must continue to find effective strategies to increase their students' cultural competence intra-culturally and cross-culturally.

Based on the research about effectively increasing cultural competence in undergraduates, we chose to employ a comprehensive three-step approach to achieve this goal with a group of undergraduates who were enrolled in a Global Awareness course. During the first part of the course, we combined an introduction to the theoretical foundation of cultural competence and identity with intentional processing activities. Students completed assigned readings, weekly reflective journal assignments, independent research, and a final identity project. They participated in guided discussions, watched videos, and visited with international guest speakers on Zoom. During the last part of the course, students participated in an interactive virtual exchange (Soliya Connect) that allowed for further processing and application. Students completed a cultural competence assessment at the beginning and at the end of the semester.

What is Culture? What is Intercultural?

The theoretical underpinnings of the word and concept of "culture" as well as the theoretical basis of "intercultural competence" were centered around the following three theoretical models: Hofstede's cultural dimensions, Milton Bennett's scale of intercultural development, and Darla Deardorff's work on intercultural competence as an outcome in various global learning contexts, such as study abroad and foreign language acquisition. The theoretical background was based on the assumption that students would need at least a basic definition of what culture actually is (or can be), as well as the language or foundations to identify and understand how culture can play a role in basic interactions. After introducing this via Hofstede (with nods to Edward T. Hall), we then discussed how these differences can cause tension when different groups interact, leading to the calls for "intercultural competence".

The Hofstede Model

The model of cultural dimensions is an enduring one which has been revisited many times in both academic and workplace or professional contexts. We spent considerable time on this model as a foundation for the course in order to give students a perspective on culture as well as cultural difference, and a vocabulary for describing their observations. There are other models which could be employed to convey similar information as each have their positives and drawbacks, but the Hofstede model also crucially separates itself from attempting to provide rigid classifications for existing national or cultural modes of interaction, instead using "synthetic cultures" to highlight the extremes or more recognizable patterns. The use of "synthetic cultures" in theorizing and identifying allows for an important degree of detachment from "real world" cultures, obviating the tendency to also apply judgements to certain cultural patterns. "Real" cultures are, of course, also not as monolithic as the dimensions may imply (Hofstede 2002). Being able to describe patterns necessarily simplifies or obscures complexities, but it also provides common vocabulary.

The Hofstede model sets up six binaries along which cultural differences play out, developed partially from Hofstede's own work within multinational corporations (where culture clashes among employees are routinely observed due to the necessity of their working together

on company goals) as well as some existing literature and research. For those unfamiliar or those who might want a refresher, the six dimensions are as follows (Hofstede 2011):

1. *Power Distance*, related to the different solutions to the basic problem of human inequality;
2. *Uncertainty Avoidance*, related to the level of stress in a society in the face of an unknown future;
3. *Individualism versus Collectivism*, related to the integration of individuals into primary groups;
4. *Masculinity versus Femininity*, related to the division of emotional roles between women and men;
5. *Long Term versus Short Term Orientation*, related to the choice of focus for people's efforts: the future or the present and past.
6. *Indulgence versus Restraint*, related to the gratification versus control of basic human desires related to enjoying life.

Although we did not necessarily emphasize a meta-discussion of these particular dimensions, nor did we directly compare them with other ideas in the course (to e.g. Hall's or Yang's), there are some potential pitfalls which bear mentioning. For example, the gendered expression of "masculinity versus femininity" as a signifier of cultural phenomenon could give modern students pause, as it may conflict with a contemporary or personal understanding of those terms as identity markers. Even the binary nature of each dimension, in other words the concept of binary poles with a graded spectrum between them, has been critiqued in the field of gender studies as a particularly "Western" approach to categorization (Beatrice 2020). Nevertheless, the Hofstede model has had longevity for a reason, and the focus here is to give students a shared vocabulary, not necessarily create new concepts.

After introducing and discussing these dimensions based on students' reading of the 2011 article, we also had them engage in some identifying activities from the 2002 book *Exploring Culture* which specifically features questions, scenarios, and activities related to the dimensions. The following are several examples, slightly edited, which illustrate more practically the ideas outlined above:

1. *A foreign consultant arrives at a meeting with a cough. Instead of starting the meeting, the hosts start to offer tea or ask if the consultant would like to borrow someone's coat.*
2. *A typical team meeting is very noisy, with people talking loudly and sometimes over one another. They do not reach an agreement during the meeting.*
3. *An Englishman visits a team abroad. The non-English team seems hesitant to answer his questions and spend a lot of time looking at the table. The CEO only nods and does not speak. Eventually only one of the employees speaks up to answer.*
4. *A business is hosting a client lunch buffet. The host business takes small portions, but refills their plate, using the same plate again. The guests follow their lead and take small portions, but when they've finished they do not take additional food.*
5. *A waiter goes to a table of visiting representatives with matching uniforms. The waiter asks the first person what she would like to drink, but before she answers,*

the whole group discusses in their own language. The first person then orders the same coffee and cake special for everyone at the table.

Some “solutions” or possible explanations are below, although of course in certain cases the students were welcome to attempt to justify other potential readings of the scenarios.

1. *Feminine (help a person in need before doing “official” business)*
2. *Individual/Masc. (each person is “equally” important, no one wants to concede)*
3. *High power distance. The participants were waiting for the nod from the CEO to give the information.*
4. *Uncertainty Avoidance. They carefully follow the hosts’ lead, but also do not wish to use a “dirty” plate a second time.*
5. *Collective. They all agree on one thing to order.*

We also used other narratives, case studies, and other materials, such as a series of graphic representations of cultural difference taken from an art book by Lui Yang, which used unique and simple graphics to compare Chinese and German cultural outlooks. These graphics also referred to the tradition of Edward T. Hall (e.g. the concept of monochronic and polychronic cultures), which also led us to introduce students to the often-discussed image of the “cultural iceberg,” popularized by Hall (see Hall 1976), which illustrates that many effects of human socialization are “below the surface” of consciousness. In other words, culture is not necessarily directly observable even by the person performing a culturally-informed act or having a culturally-informed reaction.

The above methods of introducing the concept of culture specifically as socialized patterns of behavior refer mostly to what took place in class, but additional weekly written assignments provided the impetus for more in-depth reflection on these ideas. Students were provided with additional narrative scenarios where multiple cultural factors were in play and encouraged to describe areas of tension or confusion using the terminology they had been given. They were not necessarily limited to the six dimensions; for example, students could reference the headings on Yang’s graphics, or use some terms we had referenced in less depth such as “high context versus low context communication” from Hall’s *Beyond Culture*.

Intercultural Competence

Once this groundwork had been laid, we proceeded to introduce the concept of interculturality and the idea of developing one’s cultural awareness, particularly in situations where cultural differences were at work. Even though we were still within the theoretical framework of the course (the actual online interactions taking place in the final weeks), we moved from a purely theoretical and descriptive frame of reference to one of praxis and implementation. Both Milton Bennett and Darla Deardorff are pioneers in the field of intercultural issues and regularly raise awareness of the importance of having such skills to solve problems across cultures. These were the two main authors we referenced in discussing this concept.

A Quick Aside: Terminology

As with any academic discipline, defining terms is an essential when introducing students or colleagues to new concepts. For some of the students, our course was their first introduction to

the concepts referred to variously as intercultural competence, intercultural awareness, global citizenship, and cultural intelligence, to name a few.

Table 1
Alternative Terms for Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) (Adapted from Fantini, 2006, Appendix D)

transcultural communication	international communication	ethnorelativity
cross-cultural communication	intercultural interaction	biculturalism
cross-cultural awareness	intercultural sensitivity	multiculturalism
global competitive intelligence	intercultural cooperation	plurilingualism
global competence	cultural sensitivity	effective inter-group communication
cross-cultural adaptation	cultural competence	
international competence	communicative competence	

The above chart reflects many of terms used throughout the literature, often used to describe very similar if not the same learning outcome taken from: (Sinicrope et al. 2007). Within the course, we used several phrases not quite interchangeably, but with considerable overlap due to their inherent similarities.

Deardorff: The Definition

Per Darla Deardorff's work on internationalization in higher education, the definition of intercultural competence is "the ability to develop targeted knowledge, skills, and attitudes which lead to visible behavior and communication that are both effective and appropriate in intercultural interactions" (2006). "Knowledge" is important for the identity focus of this course, as the knowledge refers not only to global issues, but also one's own personal cultural self-awareness. "Skills" refers to the ability to observe, evaluate, and empathetically react to others' perspectives, especially with the consideration that these may be culturally informed. "Attitudes" refers to personally demonstrating respect, curiosity, and openness to learning, which was one outcome we hoped the students would gain from the course, but most specifically through participation in the virtual exchange. It should also be noted that this is considered by Deardorff and the authors of this paper to be a lifelong process, and crucially one which can be influenced by the learner through "experiential learning," or the combination and recombination of observation, reflection, and practice.

Bennett: Developing the Skill

The developmental model put forth by Milton Bennett in 2004 also emphasizes that the ability to communicate, work, or otherwise cooperate across cultures is an active process. As the name implies, this is a developmental phenomenon rather than a static characteristic. The main terms that Bennett uses to characterize the development are "ethnocentric", which refers to the state of having little knowledge of or appreciation for other ways of thinking and being, versus "ethnorelative", which refers to the state of having an awareness or even understanding of other cultural modes of being. He further delineates the progression of intercultural competence (or sensitivity) with several sub-categories, moving from denial, defense and minimization to acceptance, adaptation, and integration.

The groundwork of this theory in the course served two purposes: to give students a somewhat more practical idea of what the “goal” of intercultural competence is, but also for students to consider this in light of their own identity development, which is also a process (but which can look like static characteristics). This further connects to identity because the ethnocentric categories of denial, defense, and minimization are sometimes caused by over-reliance on interpreting the world and others’ actions or responses through certain personal identity markers; in other words, the assumption that everyone’s identity is similar to one’s own, and the potential discomfort when the opposite proves true.

As with our other theoretical introductions, we used examples and narratives to illustrate the dimensions as well as the major differences between “ethnorelative” and “ethnocentric” worldviews. A classic example is the TED Talk by Chimanda Ngoze Adichie called “The Dangers of a Single Story”, which allows students to reflect on how basing an interpretation of an event on a single (such as their own) perspective flattens experience and can lead to sometimes painful misunderstandings. Identifying ways that intercultural competence can help separate some individual characteristics from culturally-informed ones, as well as being able to see that different patterns of being exist in the world, was crucial to the dynamic discussion of personal identity development which followed.

Identity Theories and Related Issues

After the introduction of theories and concepts related to cultural competence, the focus of the course shifted to establishing the connection between culture and identity. Class discussions (see Appendix) initially centered on these connections and on the definition of and elaboration on concepts such as personal, social and cultural identity, nondominant group, dominant group, nondominant identity development and dominant identity development (Communication in the Real World, 2016). This unit concluded with a journal/reflection assignment on why cultural differences matter.

Next, a video introduction to cultural identity (<https://youtu.be/Rz-zhLKOCLM>) helped students consider the complexity of cultural identity before this unit zoomed in on personal identity (which later would be reconnected to cultural identity). Erik Erikson’s (1968) theory of psychosocial development provided the foundation for this unit. Erikson’s theory consists of eight stages of psychosocial development, each linked with a particular life stage and each dominated by a specific psychosocial theme that offers a positive or a negative resolution. According to Erikson, college students are in stage five which is dominated by the conflict between identity formation and possible role confusion. The major questions of this stage are “Who am I?” and “Who am I going to be?” A positive resolution of this stage entails good self-awareness and healthy social relationships. Answering these questions and achieving a positive resolution is the developmental work of the college student. Such work requires time. Erikson (1980) asserted that the college years grant young adults the luxury of extra time that allows them to find the answers and formulate a sound sense of self.

James Marcia (1966) operationalized the following four identity statuses within the identity vs. role confusion stage of Erikson’s theory: diffusion, moratorium, foreclosure, and achievement. These statuses differ with regard to exploration and commitment. Specifically, diffusion results from low exploration and low commitment; moratorium results from high

exploration and low commitment; foreclosure results from low exploration and high commitment; and achievement results from high exploration and high commitment. The lowest status is diffusion. Along the developmental path, this status is followed either by foreclosure or moratorium, and eventually reaches achievement. Clancy and Dollinger (1993) found that moratorium is the most common status in college students, a finding that supports Erikson's original thinking. They also found that gender differences are greatest in moratorium and diffusion. Selected readings, a video, and a PowerPoint set supported the discussion of Erikson's theory and Marcia's identity statuses (see Appendix). This unit concluded with the following reflective journal assignment: "Give some thought to the class discussions about personal identity in general and identity statuses in particular. Consider which identity status best describes you in terms of your personal, social, professional/academic, and ideological identity. Write a reflection on this question, with adequate elaboration and explanation as to why you think a particular identity status describes you better than any of the others."

After examining Erikson's and Marcia's theories, we examined social identity theory and bias as the next step to returning to cultural identity and cultural competence. Henri Tajfel (1979, 1981), a Polish social psychologist, developed social identity theory which proposes that we define ourselves based on the groups to which we belong. From early childhood, a sense of belonging is important for overall psychological and emotional health. This sense of belonging enhances self-esteem and pride. However, the need to belong also leads us to categorize people by shared characteristics (i.e., we assign them to social groups). If we identify with a group, we tend to conform to their norms, and membership may enhance our self-esteem. Extreme categorization leads to the division of "us" versus "them," or in-group versus out-group, and due to social comparison, we tend to focus on the positive characteristics of in-group members but may hold negative biases toward out-group members. Subsequently, in-group members are considered superior to the out-group members, and social stereotypes and prejudice are formed.

Stereotypes have a host of negative consequences, some more subtle than others. Claude Steele, a social psychologist at Stanford University, has examined the phenomenon of stereotype threat. His TED talk on stereotype threat and identity threat is an excellent introduction to these topics for students who are unfamiliar with these concepts. Steele found that under competitive conditions, females who were high achieving in math performed about one standard deviation below males. When the competitive aspect of the situation was removed, there was no significant difference between males and females. Steele suggests that proactive attention to this issue of stereotypes and stereotype threat is needed. We need to engage in direct instruction in cultural competence. The unit on Tajfel's theory and Steele's research were supported by guided discussion, a PowerPoint presentation, videos (see Appendix), and analysis of probing questions, such as "Can you see yourself in the shoes of the in-group (out-group) member? How do you feel? (How do you feel as the "other"?). The journal prompt for that week included reflection on the following question: "If you had been in the audience for this talk, what question would you have asked Dr. Steele during the Q&A?"

Concluding activities during the in-class portion of the semester consisted of class discussions of and journal reflections on the novel *The Girl Who Fell from the Sky* by Heidi Durrow and two videos on third culture kids. The characters and events in the novel present a variety of identities at different stages of development occurring amidst trauma, bilingualism,

biculturalism, racism, intercultural issues and more. The novel offered students the opportunity to examine several of the concepts covered in class from another perspective. The two TED Talks by individuals who were third culture kids (TCKs) introduced yet another set of experiences with intercultural or multicultural issues and their developmental effects.

In order to help students integrate the knowledge they acquired during the semester and apply it to their own experiences, their final semester project was an identity self-portrait. They were encouraged to be creative with their visual representation which became each student's center piece for a brief oral presentation to the class.

Soliya Connect: Virtual Exchange

After exploring culture, socialization, and identity in theoretical and personal terms, students were given the opportunity to use some of what they had learned in interactions with an international group of students in an 8-week virtual exchange. Virtual Exchange (VE) is a practice, supported by research, that consists of sustained, technology-enabled, people-to-people education programs or activities in which constructive communication and interaction takes place between individuals or groups who are geographically separated and/or from different cultural backgrounds, with the support of educators or facilitators (Erasmus website). We were able to incorporate a virtual exchange into this course in part due to funding from the Stevens Initiative, founded by the family of Ambassador Chris Stevens after his death in Benghazi with the goal of increasing cross-cultural understanding specifically among US-based students and those from majority Muslim countries. There are many styles and methods of virtual exchange, but we specifically implemented Soliya Connect, where students from MENA (Middle East and North African) countries met with students from a variety of colleges and universities in the US, including, of course, Campbell University.

The Connect program consists of 8 weeks of dialogue facilitated by a trained, outside facilitator (i.e., not the professors of the courses in which the participating students are enrolled). The students meet weekly for two hours, beginning with meta-discussions on how to have a productive dialogue, moving on to discuss issues of global importance as identified by both the facilitators and the students themselves, and culminating in a group information-sharing session based on personal perspective and informal interviews of other local (to a given student) people. Examples of global issues can include things such as mass migration, climate change, and most recently, COVID19. The purpose and goals of the Soliya Connect program are to allow students to have contact with students who most likely would not be able to come into contact in person, and crucially, peers whose beliefs are likely very different from their own.

Participation in this program allowed students to put the previous weeks' theoretical understandings directly into practice. Not only were they able to hear directly from students who likely had very different upbringings, identities, and cultural frameworks, they were also called upon to exercise the skills and attitudes aspects of the Deardorff definition (2006), maintaining an observant and respectful role throughout the process.

Assessment of Cultural Competence

Cultural competence involves a learning process that is closely linked with individual developmental dynamics. As Erikson observed, it is during the college years when experiences have significant impact on development. Thus, in order to see whether growth occurred over the

course of the semester in the area of cultural competence, we administered the *Cultural Competence Self-Assessment Checklist* at the beginning of the semester and at the very end of the semester. This instrument was funded by Citizenship and Immigration Canada and published by the Western Center for Research &, Education on Violence Against Women & Children in Vancouver, Canada. We adapted the few Canada-specific items to U.S. culture and/or global focus. The survey contains 24 items, scored along a 4-point semantic differential scale, with possible total scores ranging from 24 to 96. Of 10 students in the class, nine completed both the pre- and the post-test. Results showed a mean increase of 9.02 points by the end of the semester. This increase represents a statistically significant difference.

Conclusion

Based on the pre- and post-assessment and based on the content of students' journals, we saw evidence that some students' cultural competence increased noticeably during the course. Student feedback on the course itself also reflected this, but as stated above, it is well-documented that many students inflate their own cultural awareness. That said, generally speaking the developmental aspects of this increased awareness or competence were captured not only in their reflections about the content presented and discussed in class, but also in their reflections about changes in their own thinking and perceptions. Several students' feedback with respect to the virtual exchange in particular showed a definite change in attitudes towards "others" or "foreigners".

We also hope that this basic premise of the three step method can be adapted to other courses and purposes. The bulk of the coursework, such as the example narratives, case studies, reflection prompts, and the discussion of a work of fiction can all be easily adapted to fit other contexts and potentially even student interests. While further study on the measurable growth or gains in cultural competence is required, as this was only intended as a pilot or "proof of concept" of the three step methodology, the pre- and post-assessment that was administered in this iteration of the course has at least shown some statistical gains in cultural competence, which is heartening. Taken together, all the signs from the course give us hope that with some tweaking of intentionality, activity and relevance of material and presentation, future sections of this course will allow us to help even more students embrace the idea of being a global citizen.

References

- Adiche, C. N. (2009, July). "The Dangers of a Single Story" [Video]. Ted Conferences. https://www.ted.com/talks/chimamanda_ngozi_adichie_the_danger_of_a_single_story?language=en
- Althen, G. (Ed.). (1994). *Learning across cultures*. Washington, DC: NAFSA.
- Beatrice, L. (2020, December 8). *The sex binary is not a 'western construct,' gender identity is*. Feminist Current. Retrieved September 14, 2021, from <https://www.feministcurrent.com/2020/12/06/the-sex-binary-is-not-a-western-construct-gender-identity-is/>
- Bennett, M. J. (2004). Becoming interculturally competent. In J.S. Wurzel (Ed.) *Toward multiculturalism: A reader in multicultural education*. Newton, MA: Intercultural Resource Corporation.
- Clancy, S. M. & Dollinger, S. J. (1993). Identity, self, and personality: Identity status and the five-factor model of personality. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 3(3), 227-245.
- Cultural Competence Self-assessment Checklist. <http://rapworkers.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/cultural-competence-selfassessment-checklist-1.pdf>
- Deardorff, D.K. (2006). A Model of Intercultural Competence and Its Implications for the Foreign Language Curriculum. In Wilkinson's *Insights from Study Abroad for Language Programs* (Thomson).
- Deardorff, D.K. (2006). Assessing Intercultural Competence in Study Abroad Students. In Byram's book *Living for Study Abroad: Theory and Practice* (Multilingual Matters).
- Derrida, Jacques. (1978) *Writing and Difference*. Trans. Alan Bass. Chicago: Univ.Chicago Press.
- Hall, E.T. (1976). *Beyond culture*. New York: Anchor Books.
- Hofstede, G. H. (2001). *Culture's consequences: Comparing values, behaviors, institutions, and organizations across nations* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing Cultures: The Hofstede Model in Context. Online Readings in Psychology and Culture, Unit 2. Retrieved from <http://scholarworks.gvsu.edu/orpc/vol2/iss1/8>
- Hofstede, G. J., Pedersen, P., & Hofstede, G. (2002). *Exploring culture: Exercises, stories, and synthetic cultures*. Yarmouth, Me: Intercultural Press.
- Erikson, E. H. (1968). *Identity, youth and crisis*. New York: Norton.
- Erikson, E. H. (1980). *Identity and the life cycle: A reissue*. New York: Norton
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development* (Vol. 1). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- "learning" (2021). In Merriam-Webster.com. Retrieved September 10, 2021, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/learning>
- Marcia, J. E. (1966). Development and validation of ego identity status. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 3(5), 551-558.
- Markey, K. & Okantey, C. (2019). Nurturing cultural competence in nurse education through a values-based learning approach. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 38, 153-156.
- Melgares, Pat (2006). "American Ways: A Guide for Foreigners in the United States and The 10 Lenses: Your Guide to Living and Working in a Multicultural World," *Journal of Applied Communications*: Vol 90. Iss 4. <https://doi.org/10.4148/10551-0834.1267>
- Meyer, Erin. (2014). *The Culture Map*. New York: Public Affairs.

- Robinson, B., & Bradley, L. (1997). Multicultural training for undergraduates: Developing knowledge and awareness. *Journal of Multicultural Counseling & Development*, 25(4), 281-289.
- Sandell, E.J., & Tupy, S.J. (2015). Where cultural competency begins: Changes on undergraduate students' intercultural competency. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 27(3), 364-381. <http://www.isetl.org/ijtlhe/>
- Sinicrope, Castle & Norris, John & Watanabe, Yukiko. (2007). *Understanding and Assessing Intercultural Competence: A Summary of Theory, Research, and Practice*. Studies in Second Language Acquisition. 26.
- Soliya Connect Program: <https://soliya.net/connect-program>
- Steele, C.M. (2010). *Whistling Vivaldi: How stereotypes affect us and what we can do*. New York: Norton.
- Tajfel, H. (1981), Social stereotypes and social groups. In J. Turner and H. Giles (Eds), (1981). *Intergroup behaviour*. (pp. 144-167). Blackwell: Oxford. Translated and reprinted in Tajfel, H. (1982). Stereotype społeczne I grupy społeczne. *Social stereotypes and social groups. Studia Psychologiczne*, 20 (2), 5-25,
- Tajfel, H. & Turner, J.C. (1979). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. In W. G. Austin & S. Worchel (Eds), *The social psychology of intergroup relations*. (pp. 33-47). Monterey, CA: Brooks Cole. Also revised as, The social identity theory of intergroup behaviour. In S. Worchel & W. G. Austin (Eds), (1986). *Psychology of intergroup relations*. (pp. 7-24). Chicago: Nelson Hall.
- Yang, Lui. (2015). *East meets West* (English & Chinese Edition) Germany: TASCHEN
- . *What is Virtual Exchange?* EVOLVE. (n.d.). Retrieved September 14, 2021, from <https://evolve-erasmus.eu/about-evolve/what-is-virtual-exchange/>.

Appendix

Cultural Competence Instruments

1. IDI version 3 (Hammer, 2009a) – 50 Likert format items – good content & construct validity and good cross cultural validity; good with people of 19th grade reading level or higher; measures ethnocentric and ethnorelativistic characteristics proposed by Bennett.

Hammer, M. R. (2009a). *The intercultural development inventory (IDI version 3)*. Berlin, MD: IDI, LLC.

2. Sampson, D.L., & Smith, H.P. (1957). A scale to measure world-minded attitudes. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 45, 99-106. [dated; possible material for update]

3. The Multicultural Awareness, Knowledge, and Skills Survey (MAKSS)*

https://drkdr counselingcourses.weebly.com/uploads/4/9/6/6/4966511/the_makss_instrument.pdf

Find initial validity and reliability information in: D'Andrea, M., Daniels, J., & Heck, R. (1991). Evaluating the impact of multicultural counseling training. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 70, 143-148.

Culture and Intercultural Resources

Week 1: “American Ways” (Melgares 2006)– students begin to see cultural assumptions of Americanness, reflection on what is “normal” (and how that is culturally bound)

Week 2: OECD 2018 PISA test “Global Citizenship” section and results report

<https://www.oecd.org/pisa/test/other-languages/pisa-2018-global-competence-test-questions.htm>

Students reflect on what “global citizenship” means, why it is relevant, what issues are “global”

Week 3: Hofstede, G. J., Pedersen, P., & Hofstede, G. (2002). *Exploring culture: Exercises, stories, and synthetic cultures*. Yarmouth, Me: Intercultural Press.

[Powerpoint with Yang’s graphics]

Week 4: We focused on the global topic of COVID19 in this section, but will adapt it to other topics in future.

Identity Resources

Week 5: *Communication in the Real World* (2016). Foundations of Culture and Identity, Ch. 8.1, University of Minnesota Libraries. <https://open.lib.umn.edu/communication/chapter/8-1-foundations-of-culture-and-identity/>

Reflection assignment: In this week's reading, review the section that explains why difference matters. Discuss the ways in which difference may influence how you communicate in each of the following contexts: personal (with friends and family), academic (with peers and teachers), and professional (i.e., at your job; if you don't have a job, make this a hypothetical).

Week 6: Videos on basic identifiers of cultural identity (focus on complexity of concept) and connection to personal identity

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=Rz-zhLKOCLM>

Cherry, K. (2021). Identity vs. Role Confusion in Psychosocial Development. Verywellmind.

<https://www.verywellmind.com/identity-versus-confusion-2795735>

Cramer, P. (2000). Development of identity: Gender makes a difference. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 34, 42-72. doi: 10.1006/jrpe.1999.2270

Week 7: Video on “Stereotype Threat and Identity Threat: The Science of a Diverse Community.” A presentation by Claude Steele at the MIT Media Lab.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=HKxkI2WVEWQ>

Week 8: Video on “How to Outsmart Your Own Unconscious Bias.” TEDxTalks. You Tube. Valerie Alexander speaks about bias with regard to gender, race, and sexual orientation. She discusses the brain mechanisms involved in responding to unfamiliar situations (i.e., stress and bias). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?app=desktop&v=GP-cqFLS8Q4>

Week 9: Durrow, Heidi. (2010). *The Girl Who Fell from the Sky*. Chapel Hill, NC: Algonquin Books.

Videos: Third Culture Kids

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GTSmPne279c>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8RCmgMKJRy8>

Final Project: Identity

Soliya Connect Program: <https://soliya.net/connect-program>